

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF A GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR LOCATING LEAKS ON UNDERGROUND TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE – PART WATER SUPPLY

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Abstract

In the current versions of the two fundamental documents which are defining the management and development of the Water Sector in the Republic of Bulgaria – "National Strategy for Management and Development of the Water Sector" and "Strategy for Development and Management of Water Supply and Sewerage Systems in the Republic of Bulgaria", the main problems related to the bursts and water losses in the Water Supply Network, as well as the insufficient maintenance of Water Supply Systems and facilities, are clearly identified as the main ones. The water losses found in these documents are classified as large, assuming that they are mainly due to real leaks – both visible and hidden in the underground technical infrastructure. The main purpose of this publication is to be presented the conceptual model of a geographic information system for locating water leaks with a focus on the Water Supply Network and the problems on the latter related not only to the localization of leaks from the underground technical infrastructure, but also for the structuring of the water leaks related information. The conceptual model will be presented through the applicable ISO/TC 211 standards in the field of digital geographic information from the point of view of applying the principles and approaches of the systems approach.

Keywords: water leak, GIS, ISO/TC 211, UML Class Diagrams, Conceptual model, Meta-meta model level, Meta model level.

1. Introduction

At the time of this analysis, there are 40 Water Supply and Sewerage Operators on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria with different ownership of the companies (35% are entirely state-owned; 28% are entirely municipal-owned; 37% are mixed ownership – state and municipal). There are also 28 Associations of Water Supply and Sewerage in separate territories, according to the provision of Art. 198b of the Water Act [1]. At present, there is no legal framework that regulates uniform basic requirements for the creation of a Geographic Information System (GIS) for the needs of water supply and sewerage operators, which leads to a multitude of currently available GIS with non-standardized databases, layers and attributes to them. This, in turn, is an important prerequisite for the difficult water asset management and development of the Water Sector [2], water supply and sewerage in the country – [3] and [4].

Based on the analysis of the main documents cited above, it can be concluded that there is an unsatisfactory share of standardized implementation of: water asset registers and/or GIS; registers of water meters, water supply connections; databases/registers for personnel; unmeasured legal consumption; control flow meters and data loggers. As a major unresolved problem, the problems related to the water leaks can also be pointed on the underground technical infrastructure, incl. their reliable pinpointing of the leaks and losses measurement.

The purpose of this publication is to present a Meta-meta data level and a standardized Metadata level (presented in [5]) for locating leaks on the Water Supply Network (WSN) - both visible and hidden on the underground technical infrastructure.

2. Research methodology

The implementation of GIS, in principle, should lead to better management and reduce the time for making adequate management decisions. Properly structured data that is part of GIS should significantly improve the exchange of data/information between different external and internal users, as well as to minimize potential errors.

The data sources used so far by Water Supply and Sewerage Operators are different, with the largest part contained in maps and schemes on traditional media (most often on paper), there are available AutoCAD DWG and/or ESRI SHP files, as well as text documents, etc. With this information in mind, the main problems of Water Supply and Sewerage operators (WSSO) related to the data on the WSN that are used can be summarized as follows:

- Much of the information is on paper (paper maps), which, in addition to being old and outdated, are often in poor physical condition;
- Different scale (and hence the different accuracy of the data (both in position and height, as well as in detail, content, time, completeness, presentation and visualization). In urbanized areas, the available maps/digital models are usually at a scale of 1:5 000, while for non-urbanized areas (meaning the supply

main water pipes) they are usually at a scale of 1:25 000 or 1:100 000;

- There are settlements for which there is no any kind of information about the WSN and the facilities on it, i.e. In the event of an accident in this case, the exact location of the underground infrastructure is not known;
- AutoCAD DWG and/or ESRI SHP files are available for part of the WSN, but for these digital models there are no uniform requirements for their drawings, structuring and visualization;
- Some of the assets (each asset has an identifier) are supported in Excel spreadsheets, but in different versions of this product. In practice, asset identifiers are not tied to the respective spatial object (pipe, facility, etc.), which in turn leads to difficulties in maintaining the current state of the same;
- In most cases, the required procedures for data exchange between the departments in the WSSOs are missing or not maintained;
- No history of events related to the sites and facilities of the WSN is maintained;
- In some of the water supply and sewerage operators, digitized data of the WSN and facilities are available, but in general the methodology used and engineering validation of the accuracy of the data, etc., are not clear.

From what has been said so far, it is clear that GIS for locating leaks on the underground technical infrastructure with a focus on the WSN is a complex, complex information system. The conceptual model presented below will be presented in accordance with the approaches and recommendations of ISO Technical Committee 211 (ISO/TC 211) - Geographic information/ Geomatics [6] by creating a reference conceptual model within the meaning of the ISO/TC 211 approach cited, i.e. compliance with the principles of the system approach in the implementation of the principle of synergy.

The methodology presented in this way (implemented through Meta-meta data level and Meta data level) guarantees the realism of obtaining reliable results, while providing opportunities to compare the results obtained with known ones in the subject area under consideration.

3. Results

3.1. Meta-meta data level

The Meta-meta data level presented below is in accordance with the guidelines presented in [5] and after the analysis of the studied issues based on the regulatory framework ([7]) and the lecture courses on Water Supply held at University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy, Sofia, Bulgaria – Faculty of Hydraulic Engineering. The terms and terminology used are in accordance with [8].

In Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community Rev. 2 (2008): Level 1 Codes – Code E, Water Supply; Sewerage, Waste Management and Remediation Activities, Water Supply is defined as water collection, treatment and supply [9]. Water Supply activities cover groundwater, surface and rainwater that needs to be treated, and the delivery

is to consumers in a type - domestic, industrial or agricultural.

The elements of water supply [10] (from the point of view of the issues under consideration) can be classified as:

- Water intake facility for capturing and supplying water while preserving its natural qualities to the water supply system. The main types are: catchments, wells, drains and water intake towers;
- Extraction tank, which must be located in front of the pumping station, in order to equalize the water flow and the pumped water quantity in accordance with the accepted mode of operation of the pumps, which are subdivided into centrifugal and volumetric;
- A pumping station is a pumping facility to ensure the appropriate pressure and water quantity in the water supply system;
- A water treatment plant is a complex of facilities for treatment of raw natural water in order to ensure the regulatory requirements for the quality of water before its supply to the water pipelines;
- Pressure regulation valve is a facility for equalizing the relatively constant inflow and variable consumption of water at certain times of the day and can be of the following type: pressure tank, water tower or hydrophore;
- External water pipeline is a water pipeline that transports water from the water source to the Water Treatment Plant and the WSN in the water supply area;
- WSN is a network of water pipelines in the water supply area for the supply of the necessary water quantities to consumers. It consists of main, secondary and building water supply deviations;
- Common water measuring devices that are necessary for water abstraction, purification, storage, transmission, distribution and measurement of water up to the Water Service Connection of the building or water supply system or the internal (site) WSN of consumers;
- A sanitary protection zone that provides protection against manifestations of terrorism, vandalism and other actions aimed at destroying the integrity of the facilities and polluting drinking water.

Water losses due to emptying of the WSN during the construction of Water Service Connections, as well as during flushing, disinfection and elimination of breakdowns in the water supply system represent the technical losses of water in the water supply systems.

Water leaks can be categorized into three categories: on water main pipelines and distribution networks; leakage or overflow from storage tanks; at the Water Service Connection. In every WSN, there are losses that must be within controlled limits.

For each WSN, information must be stored about different events (commissioning, decommissioning, accidents, repairs and activities for elimination of accidents/leaks, etc.).

For each element of the WSN, position and height data shall be stored in the respective reference coordinate and altitude systems. The same should be done for leaks and bursts. For the performed repair works, data on the performed geodetic measurements and executives must be stored.

Certain metadata must be stored for all: elements of the WSN, bursts and repairs, as well as for detected leaks.

3.2. Meta data level

The Metadata level was created with Sparx Systems Enterprise Architect. The Metadata level (see pictures 1, 2, 3a to 3f, 4 and 5 below) is in accordance with ISO 19103:2015 Geographic information – Conceptual schema language standard, part of ISO/TC 211, [6].

Pic. 1. Class - Relation of the Water Supply System (WSS) to the Cadastre and Spatial development in Bulgaria.

Pic. 2. Class - Basic elements and relations of Water Supply System (WSS)

Pic. 3a. Detailing of basic elements and relations of Water Supply System (WSS) – class Water Supply Network

Pic. 3b. Detailing of basic elements and relations of Water Supply System (WSS) – class Shaft

Pic. 3c. Detailing of basic elements and relations of Water Supply System (WSS) – class Reservoir

Pic. 3d. Detailing of basic elements and relations of Water Supply System (WSS) – class Water source

Pic. 3e. Detailing of basic elements and relations of Water Supply System (WSS) – class Pumping station

Pic. 3f. Detailing of basic elements and relations of Water Supply System (WSS) – class Regulating water pressure facility

Pic. 4. Class - High level diagram of the domain of Water Supply System (WSS)

Pic. 5 Geometry representation of Water supply objects – class UML geometry representation

4. Discussion

Picture 1 shows the relationship of the WSS with the Cadastre and Spatial development of the country. The Cadastre and Spatial Development classes are expressed through: the Cadastre and Property Register Act - [11], the Spatial Development Act - [4] and associated regulations. The relevant inheritance relationships for these two base classes with their respective subclasses (derived classes) are provided.

Picture 2 presents the main elements and their corresponding relationships in the WSS. Five base and 15 subclasses are identified in accordance with current regulations. Pictures from 3a to 3f further details the subclasses and the relationships for the identified Water Source and Facility base classes, which are critical to the issues at hand.

Picture 4 represents the WSS domain in the form of a high level diagram in accordance with the current concepts of ISO/TC 211 standards in the field of digital geographic information [6]. The WSS Event class (part of the WSS dataset base class) is identified, which will contain the necessary information about located leaks on underground technical infrastructure - part Water Supply. The events along with the other elements of the diagram are implemented using the normalized reference coordinate and elevation systems and the corresponding plotting rule in these reference systems.

Finally, Picture 5 details the geometric representation of Water supply objects, including Event class objects, using the established reference coordinate system.

5. Conclusion

The presented Meta-meta data level and Meta data level is in accordance with:

- Principles of the systemic approach that leads to the achievement of synergy and
- Applicable set of generally accepted standards for information on objects or phenomena that are directly or indirectly related to a location relative to the

Earth – for this publication these are the standards of ISO/TC 211 Geographic information/Geomatics.

This is a reliable prerequisite for the successful implementation of the next two levels, namely: Application schema level (application schemas) - define the types of objects, data, and processing; Data level - contains the data that is defined by the application schema level.

The Application schema and Data levels, as well as the required mathematical model for the located leaks on underground technical infrastructure - part Water Supply, are moving to be implemented in an ArcGIS software environment in the near future.

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